

IN-SITU STRAIN MONITORING OF 3-D WOVEN COMPOSITES USING INTEGRATED FIBER OPTIC SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this work was to demonstrate monitoring of internal strains using fiber optic sensors integrated within the reinforcement of 3-D woven composites. The unique feature of the project was that optical sensors were woven in as the preform was fabricated, allowing the sensors to nest intimately within the tows, including tows in through-thickness direction. Addressed herein are the 4-point bending and lap-shear testing of 3-D woven composite specimens with woven-in sensors, procedures used for strain monitoring, and comparison of the results with data from foil gage used for reference. The optical sensors measured strains in X, Y, and Z axes which correlate with data from foil gages. Optic sensor data was then used to determine the in-plane and through-thickness shear moduli for the 3-D woven fabric composite. A sensor located near an open hole detected elevated strains. Sensors near the "step" in the shear sample captured the nonlinear load-strain responses, as did foil gages mounted on the sample surface. Sensors located near/within fiber tows recorded "stiffer" responses, as expected, compared to foil gages overlapping several unit cells. Also discussed are some additional capabilities this new approach provides and why some difference in strains monitored by fiber optic sensors and foil gages may be seen.

KEYWORDS: 3-D woven composite, fiber optic strain sensor, flex test, tensile test.

INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional woven preforms are potential means for the manufacture of light-weight, damage tolerant, durable and cost-effective structural composites. As recently explored in [1], [2], 3-D woven textile reinforcements also provide unique opportunities for in-situ health monitoring of composite structures. The measurement of strains within the unit cells and tows is particularly critical in predicting the behavior of 3-D textile composites, which should be more rigorously treated as complex structures, rather than as homogeneous materials. Detailed data may be critical in allowing modeling at a micro-(unit cell) level across large structures to keep pace with available computing power. Further, the measurement of strains imposed on the load-bearing tows within composite material under load, carries direct benefits in the manufacture, inspection, maintenance, management, and control of primary structural components.

The overall goal of this research was to demonstrate capability of monitoring of internal strains using fiber optic sensors integrated within the reinforcement of 3-D woven composites. The unique feature of this work is that optical sensors were woven in as the preform was fabricated, allowing the sensors to nest intimately within the tows, including out-of-plane tows. The details particular to the manufacture of 3-D woven fabric preforms and composites instrumented with Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometry (EFPI) fiber optic sensors were recently reported in [1], [2]. The present paper is focused alternatively on the

mechanical testing of the fabricated 3-D orthogonal composites and the interpretation of strains monitoring results.

The specific project segments to be discussed herein are 4-point bending and lap-shear testing of 3-D orthogonal specimens with woven-in sensors, the procedures used for strain monitoring, and comparison of the results with data from foil gages used for reference. The optical sensors measured strains in X, Y, and Z axes, which are compared with data from foil gages. In the large volume of work (reported in the literature) using “embedded” sensors, the sensors are, typically, in-plane oriented and placed within the resin-rich interphase between the fiber reinforced plies. Contrary to that, integration of the sensors during weaving fabric preform results in their intimate nesting among the tow filaments. The sensors can then provide the strain monitoring needed at the unit cell level.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Mechanical tests (bending and lap-shear) were conducted with two objectives in mind. The first was to validate the functionality of the integrated fiber optic strain sensors after weaving and resin infusion. Bending tests were then run to demonstrate that the sensors read strain accurately. The second objective was to compare, for the first time ever, internal strain measurements in a textile preform to the external strain measurements provided by surface-mounted foil gauges.

3-D WEAVING

The 3-D weaving approach invented in [3] and used in this work is much more gentle to the fibers than conventional 2-D weaving, thus enabling integration of optical fibers during weaving. A conventional 2-D weaving process (illustrated in Figure 1) crimps all fiber tows, which causing severe signal losses. On the other hand, in the process [3] (illustrated in Figure 2) the in-plane tows (X – “warp” and Y – “weft”) remain practically straight within the preform, and only “through-the-thickness” Z tows are significantly bent at the preform surfaces. The other reason is that in the 3-D weaving process [3], individual warp tow layers do not pass through heddles, and so are not dragged across sharp heddle edges, or forced to repeatedly cross neighboring warp yarn layers.

Figure 1. Schematic of conventional 2-D weaving.

Figure 2. 3-D Orthogonal Weaving with EFPIs.

It is also important that 3-D integral woven composites do not delaminate or allow for usual growth of cracks, hence providing much safer environment for optical sensors. In principle, three normal strain components can be monitored at any location within the structure. The approach provides a unique capability for monitoring internal “peel” strain which is especially valuable in the cases of composite bonded and bolted joints, holes, notches, openings, stiffeners, and in other cases of high strain gradients.

FIBER OPTIC SENSORS

Despite the advantages of 3-D weaving for fiber optic sensor integration, there are certain shortcomings that are inherent to the commercially available optical fibers themselves. A notable challenge encountered in the present work is that breakage of optical fibers at/below the surface of the composite can prevent re-establishment of an optical connection to the interrogation device, effectively leading to the loss of the sensor. Careful and precise handling of the sensor and sensor leads was essential in successful instrumentation of the fabricated composite samples.

In this work, Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometry (EFPI) strain sensors were selected for weaving into 3-D preforms. The EFPI in particular is less suited to weaving as compared to intrinsic sensors, but carry certain advantages valuable in this study. EFPI-based sensors use a distance measurement technique based on the formation of a low-finesse Fabry-Perot cavity between the end face of an optical fiber and a reflective surface. Luna Innovations, Blacksburg, VA, USA produces instrumentation which measures the air cavity size to a resolution of 200 picometers over an air gap size range of more than 100 microns, thereby resulting in a potential resolution of better than 0.0002% full-scale. The impressive range and resolution provided by this type of sensor/system can be used to measure virtually any physical phenomenon that can be transformed into a displacement of the EFPI air cavity [4]. Previously, the EFPI sensor technology has been extensively tested and demonstrated good fatigue properties, robustness, and accurate strain measurements, see for example [5]. EFPI sensors have low thermal sensitivity (approximately $0.5 \text{ me}/^\circ\text{C}$) [6]. They are extrinsic, meaning the sensing occurs in the air gap outside of the optical fiber. Optical properties of air in the EFPI air cavity won't change with the application of transverse strain [5]. Results obtained in [7] show that this type of optical fiber sensors is less sensitive to transverse strain components compared to intrinsic-type optical sensors, such as Bragg gratings.

Standard EFPI sensor body is approximately 8–10 mm long. Shorter sensors were needed to fit within the thickness of the test specimens fabricated in the framework of this research, and thus their length approached the unit cell dimensions in the 3-D weave. Sensors with gauge length of 2mm were manufactured by Luna Innovations, Inc., and used in this work. The ratio of the length of the sensor to the gap size determines the gauge factor. The gap is usually set near 55 microns, as this is advantageous relative to the wavelength of the drive frequency applied.

MANUFACTURE OF BENDING SPECIMENS

Four-point bend tests were selected for three primary reasons. Firstly, four-point bend specimen construction is not complicated (a simple prismatic beam of appropriate aspect ratio). Secondly, stress state in this type of specimen is well understood (pure bending between the inner supports results in roughly linear variation of longitudinal stress through the thickness). Thirdly, options for optical fiber egress points are plentiful (essentially all surfaces and edges are free and available for egress). Bending specimens also included surface-mounted foil strain gages (placed on top, bottom, and edge surfaces).

A relatively thick (0.65 inch) integral T300 carbon fiber preform was woven with 7 warp and 8 weft yarn layers, including several sets of fiber optic sensors woven in the warp, weft, and Z directions. The fiber volume content in the respective directions was 17%, 17%, and 14% (total fiber volume fraction 48%). The optical sensors were woven into the 2nd and 4th warp layers as well as the central Z corridor (dent). Placement of the sensors is shown schematically in Figure 3. A fragment of the preform with woven-in sensors and edge connectors is shown in Figure 4. To circumvent the egress issue, bend specimens were woven with connectors at one end of the sensor assemblies and subsequently infused. A non-curing silicone grease was employed to exclude the resin from the connectors and act as a release agent against surrounding matrix material. Derakane 8084 Epoxy-Vinyl Ester resin was selected for the composite

matrix due to its short cure time at room temperature. Room temperature cure also reduced thermal stresses between the resin and tows.

Two preforms were used to fabricate bend specimens labeled B001 through B004. Resin infusion was performed using Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) between two polyethylene tool surfaces. Infused preforms remained in the vacuum bag and under an electric blanket at 90°C for two hours as a precaution against localized residual thermal stresses. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the preform with the woven-in fibers and connectors under the vacuum bag in VARTM process and one of several test specimens cut from a single panel.

Figure 3. Schematic of sensor placement.

Figure 4 Preform with end connectors.

Figure 5. Preform in vacuum bag.

Figure 6. Infused bending test specimen.

FOUR-POINT BEND TESTING

Four specimens were prepared for bending tests. They were nominally 12 inches long x 2 inches wide x 0.65 inches thick. Three resistance-type foil strain gages (350 ohm) were also mounted to each specimen

for strain comparison purposes. Foil gages with lengths of 0.5 inches and 0.125 inches were mounted in the longitudinal direction on the specimen bottom and a gage of length 0.062 inch was mounted vertically at the center of the specimen edge. All gages were mounted using MBOND 200 adhesive. The 0.5-inch gage covered approximately five unit cells and gave an "average" response over these cells. The 0.125-inch gage was mounted a short distance longitudinally from the 0.5-inch gage and provided a "local" response relative to a single unit cell. The 0.062-inch gage mounted on the edge was intended to capture z-direction strains, although these strains were anticipated to be small.

The location of each fiber optic sensor and the pathways of each lead in the X–Y plane were determined by means of x–radiography and measurements subsequently taken from bitmap images of the resulting films. An example of the radiographs, produced using a 75kV source, is shown in Figure 7. The larger dimension in the width direction reduced the relative effect of the glass sensors on the total mass absorption in that axis. The resulting contrast was insufficient to determine accurately the Z–positions of the sensor head. Their locations were determined only to within their respective weft layers.

The 4-point bending fixture support dimensions measured 4.0 inches on the inside support span and 10.0 inches on the outer support span, see Figure 8. These dimensions were chosen to provide sufficient space for any stress concentrations under the loading noses to dissipate prior to reaching the sensors and foil gages. Each specimen was loaded into the fixture, centered, and aligned. Foil gages and optical sensors were zeroed. Foil gage strain data, load cell data, and crosshead displacement data were collected by one computer at a rate of 10 samples per second. Due to the optical sensors data acquisition equipment could not process data from the strain gages or load cell, load was applied through manual control of the hydraulic actuator in quasi-static increments of 100 lb. The load was held for several seconds before the next increment was applied. While this procedure created a "stair-step" appearance to the strain-time and load-time data, it allowed the data collected by the two separate pieces of equipment to be accurately correlated after testing.

Figure 7. Example radiograph.

Figure 8. Bending specimen in load frame.

The readings from the optical sensors were converted to strains, and displayed live during the tests. However, due to significant data manipulation was required to convert optical data readings to the desired strain data, several optical strain data streams were collected at a rate of approximately 0.5 samples/second each.

Longitudinal strain data for the four specimens are shown in Figures 9–11. Fiber optic data for Specimen 004 are not reported because the leads to the integrated longitudinal fiber optic sensor were damaged. Figures 9–11 also include calculations of the modulus of the material as obtained from the 0.5-inch foil gage and from the integrated optical sensor closest to the sample surface. Stress calculation in the case of

the foil gages was based on traditional strength-of-materials equations for the bending moment in the beam and the distance between the outer beam surface and its neutral axis. As mentioned before, X-rays could not provide the exact through thickness location of the sensor. Hence, stresses in the integrated fiber optic sensor case could only be approximated based on the information about the weft yarn layer in which the sensors were integrated (i.e., the approximated distance from the sensor to the beam neutral axis).

The consistency among experimental data obtained for the Specimens 3, 5, and 6 (particularly, in the relative location of the curves) is surprising. The 0.5-inch gage provides longitudinal tensile modulus for the material between 4.4 and 5.3 Msi, while the 0.125-inch gage results are consistently lower and the optical sensor results are consistently higher (in one case, 77% higher). Close examination of the 0.125-inch gages shows the majority of the grid to be located over a matrix pocket, which results in a higher strain for a given stress. Meanwhile, the stiffer response of the 0.125-inch gage on Specimen 4 (not shown) can be attributed to its location over a fiber bundle. While it is not possible to verify at this time, it is hypothesized that the larger apparent stiffness provided by the optical sensors is related to its proximity to the respective yarn. Indeed, the closer the sensor is to the yarn, the higher the apparent stiffness of the reading is, since the EFPI sensor may suffer only as much strain as the surrounding material (in this case, fibers of the corresponding yarn). This is exactly the type of behavior anticipated for the optical sensor, and in fact, this is the desired behavior for investigating material response on the unit cell level.

Figure 9. Longitudinal gage and sensor data for Specimen 003.

Figure 10. Longitudinal gage and sensor data for Specimen 005.

Figure 11. Longitudinal gage and sensor data for Specimen 006.

After completion of testing for Specimen 003, a 0.25-inch diameter hole was drilled through the specimen in the vicinity of the integrated sensors (see Figure 12), and then the specimen was re-tested in bending. The objective of this experiment was to introduce a stress concentration in the material and verify that it could be recorded by the integrated sensors. Figure 13 shows a comparison of the optical sensor strains recorded before the hole was drilled (same as in Figure 10) and after the hole was drilled. Figure 13 shows clearly that the optical sensor remained intact during the drilling procedure and was able to record the presence of increased strain near the hole. For a given level of bending load the specimen with the hole strained more than the one without the hole.

Figure 12. Center hole drilled near optical sensor.

Figure 13. Strain increase detected by optical sensor.

LAP JOINT TESTING SIMULATION

Lap joint testing simulation was performed using specimens made from the sensor instrumented flat composite panels by machining 0.1 inch deep "steps" symmetrically about the centerline. The specimens nominally measured 12 inches long x 1 inch wide x 0.3 inches thick (Figure 14). Lap shear specimens included small foil gages attached to the side faces. Testing was conducted at quasi-static rates. Each specimen contained between one and three operational optical sensors oriented vertically in the thick section of the specimen near the step. Each also contained one sensor oriented axially within the thin

section. Figure 15 shows radiographs of the two specimens and demonstrates that despite low contrast due to large dimension in the thickness direction, contrast is still sufficient to accurately determine sensor location in all three directions. Vertically oriented foil strain gages (0.125 in. long) also were mounted to specimen edges.

Figure 14. Schematic of stepwise specimen geometry.

Figure 15. Radiographs of step specimens.

Because the data acquisition systems recording optical sensor and foil gage outputs were physically separate, it was necessary to manually load the specimens in increments of load in order to correlate the strain data. Figure 16 and Figure 17 show the loading histories for Specimens 001t and 002t, respectively. (Note that the "t" designates an elastic loading-unloading cycle to 5000 lb. Both specimens were later tested to failure during subsequent loading).

Figure 16. First stepwise loading of Specimen 001t.

Figure 17. First stepwise loading of Specimen 002t.

Similar stepwise behavior was also apparent in the strain histories recorded from the axially oriented optical gages (Figure 18 and Figure 19). Strain-Load plots were constructed by directly matching load values to axial strain values at each plateau. Strain data from the Z-sensors were too near the noise level, and nonlinear to take advantage of plateaus. To construct strain-load plots for these data, the time value at the approximate midpoint of each plateau was indexed to an "average" Z-sensor strain. This average strain was taken as the value that matched-up with the load at the plateau. The "average" strain was constructed by calculating a running block-mean of 21 data points surrounding each point (10 points to either side of the point plus the point itself). The running average is depicted in Figure 18 and Figure 19.

Figure 20 and Figure 21 show the resulting strain-load data for Specimens 001t and 002t, respectively. The data are plotted in this manner since the testing was performed under loading control and some of the

strains reverse sign as the load increases. Note that when data are presented in this form, steeper slopes actually mean *lower* apparent stiffness. Figure 20 and Figure 21 reveal some interesting results.

Figure 18. Stepwise loading of Specimen 001t.

Figure 19. Stepwise loading of Specimen 002t.

Figure 20. Strain-Load response for stepwise Specimen 001t.

Figure 21. Strain-Load response for stepwise Specimen 002t.

The short foil gage placed near the step did not compare consistently with the longer foil gage and those both were not close enough to the step to register the stress concentration. The short foil gage was mounted similarly on both specimens (directly over an exposed warp tow), yet the slopes for the short and long gages compare well in one case (002t) but not in the other (001t).

2. The axially mounted optical sensors consistently show smaller slope compared to the foil gages, yielding an apparently higher stiffness. This behavior is consistent with the bending specimens and is attributed to the proximity of the optical gages to a stiff fiber yarn.
3. The Z-sensors display an unexpected nonlinear behavior, actually reversing sign as the load is increased. Due to such behavior is consistent for both the optical sensors and foil gages, there is some confidence that it is a physical effect, not an artifact of data reduction. The optical sensors, which are internal to the specimen, remain under compression considerably longer than the Z-gages on the surface. The reasons for this effect are not immediately clear. The obtained data, however, do not show that the closer the optical Z-sensor is to the step, the sooner it transitions from compression to tension: sensor Z1, closest to the step, transitions at around 2750 lb (for Specimen 001t), while sensor Z2 transitions at around 3750 lb (for Specimen 002t), and sensor Z3, the farthest from the step, transitions at 4500 lb (for Specimen 002t). It can be speculated that a combination of geometrical nonlinearity and/or inelastic material behavior (both affecting transverse shear and peel stresses near the step) are responsible for the observed effects.

SUMMARY

The overall goal of demonstrating strain measurement using fiber optic sensors within the reinforcement of woven composites was successfully achieved. Optical sensors were woven into the preforms, survived resin infusion, and measured internal strains within the yarns of bending and stepwise specimens. A sensor located near an open hole detected elevated strains near the hole. Sensors near the "step" in the lap joint simulating specimens captured nonlinear load-strain responses, as also did foil gages mounted on the specimen surfaces. Sensors located near fiber tows recorded a comparatively stiff response, vs. the foil gages mounted over several fabric composite unit cells. Further analysis of micro-structural effects is currently underway to better understand the internal strain variations with increasing load level, as

revealed by experimental data captured from within these intricate structures commonly called “textile composite materials”.

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